

Mediatised Conflicts and Digital Witnessing: A Study of Palestinian Narratives on TikTok in the Gaza Occupation in 2023

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In today's digital age, the synergy between social media and mainstream media has transformed the landscape of political communication, highlighting the need for a comprehensive understanding of both media's influences on public engagement and democratic participation. Scholars have extensively studied the use of social media platforms such as Facebook and YouTube as tools for amplifying voices, shaping public discourse, and holding governments accountable. The rise of TikTok as the most popular social media platform among Generation Z has transformed political communication, indicating the need for further research in this area. Drawing from theories of mediatized conflicts and digital witnessing, this article contributes to discussions on how TikTok has emerged as a platform for the documentation and dissemination of the realities of conflicts by civilians. It does so by conducting a discourse analysis of 230 TikTok videos documenting events in Gaza from October to December 2023. This article shows the particularities of how the Palestinian community has articulated their struggles online as a diasporic community, and how they have used TikTok as a site of resistance. Additionally, it shows the large array of surveillance strategies that the Israeli government has in place to control the narrative of the events, and the tactics that Palestinians have developed to avoid algorithmic filtering, censorship, and surveillance.

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, the synergy between social media and mainstream media has transformed the landscape of political communication, highlighting the need for a comprehensive understanding of both media's influences on public engagement and democratic participation. While the relevance of mainstream media in shaping public opinion and informing political discourse is recognised and widely documented, the growing importance of social media platforms has revolutionised political communication, offering individuals unprecedented avenues for engagement and expression (Hayes, 2023). Social media's interactive nature enables citizens to connect, share information, and mobilise support around political issues with greater speed and reach than ever before (Eskjaer et al., 2015). From hashtag campaigns to viral videos, platforms like X, Facebook, and Instagram have become powerful tools for amplifying voices, shaping public discourse, and holding governments accountable (Kaempf, 2013).

Furthermore, the emergence of TikTok as a dominant social media platform has further expanded the landscape of political participation. With its short-form video format and a massive user base of over one billion monthly users (Dean, 2023), TikTok offers a unique space for political expression and engagement (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022). The platform's algorithmic features, such as the "For You" page, amplify content based on user preferences, increasing the visibility of political content to diverse audiences (Perez et al., 2023). As a result, TikTok has become an effective tool for grassroots movements, enabling individuals to bypass traditional gatekeepers and reach global audiences with their political messages (Hayes, 2023). For instance, during the Black Lives Matter movement, the #StopAsianHate campaign during the COVID-19 pandemic (Cervi et al., 2022), and the Russia-Ukraine war (Vidal Egea, 2022), TikTok emerged as a powerful platform for raising awareness and mobilising support. The impact of TikTok during these movements highlighted its importance as a driver of social justice activism and collective mobilisation in the digital era, underlining the need for additional examination.

More recently, TikTok has become a vital tool for individuals living in Gaza to share their lived experiences, struggles, and resistance against the Israeli occupation with a global audience (Abbas et al., 2022; Cervi et al., 2022; Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022; Hayes, 2023). In conducting a discourse analysis of

230 TikTok videos from Gaza between October and December 2023, this article seeks to examine the role of TikTok in documenting and amplifying the voices of those affected by the Israeli occupation of Gaza following the last escalation of hostilities in October 2023.

Chapter 1 introduces the relevance of the topic and briefly outlines the historical background of the situation in Gaza leading up to the ongoing events. Chapter 2 provides the theoretical framework of the article, as well as an overview of the existing literature about the mediatisation of conflict (Eskjaer et al., 2015), digital witnessing and its challenges and critical debates (Chouliaraki, 2015; Gregory, 2015; Harlow, 2017), and it briefly frames the Palestinian struggle on TikTok (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022; Abbas et al., 2022; Hayes, 2023). Chapter 3 outlines the approach and methods used to conduct the research. It includes a positionality statement, details about the data collection process and the coding process, as well as validity and ethical considerations regarding the study. Chapter 4 evaluates the findings of the analysis, supplementing them with screenshots from some of the videos to illustrate the results. This chapter demonstrates that the platform is used by Palestinian civilians to amplify their voices and reach new audiences through the creative use of language and TikTok affordances such as music to challenge Israeli narratives through the articulation of their own narrative frames and to avoid mainstream media gatekeepers through the use of innovative techniques to evade censorship. Lastly, Chapter 5 concludes by summarising the results, as well as considering the limitations of the research and potential ways to expand the study in the future.

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

It is beyond the scope of the present research to provide an in-depth account of the literature concerning the Israeli occupation of Gaza. For that reason, this short chapter will only briefly outline the main events that have led to the escalation of hostilities beginning on 7 October 2023.

The State of Palestine, officially recognised as a non-member observer state by the United Nations since 2012, is situated between the Jordan River and the Mediterranean Sea (UN, 2024). As illustrated in Image 1, this territory consists of two areas of land, the Gaza Strip and the West Bank, which are physically separated by the State of Israel. Israel has maintained varying degrees of control over these territories since the Six-Day War in 1967 (Hayes, 2023). Over 140 UN member states recognise Palestine as a sovereign state; however, it lacks full UN membership, and its statehood remains a subject of international debate (UN, 2024). As a result, Palestine continues to grapple with Israeli occupation, territorial fragmentation, and the ongoing quest for self-determination.

Palestine was under Ottoman rule from the sixteenth century until World War I, when the Ottoman Empire collapsed; following this, Britain assumed its control by signing the Sykes-Picot Accord with France in 1916 (Shihade, 2012). This inaugurated the so-called British Mandate, which would establish the economic, social, and political infrastructures needed for the future state of Israel (Hayes, 2023; Shihade, 2012).

Image 1: Gaza Strip access and movement (September 2023) Source: United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA)

As nationalism gained momentum in Europe, Jews started to view their shared religious and racial characteristics as forming a distinct Jewish identity or "nationality;" this perception contributed to the development of the idea of a Jewish nation, indicating a collective identity beyond just religious or cultural affiliation (Sayegh, 2012, p. 207). This Jewish nation included traditional national rights, such as the right to create a Jewish state and the right to separate existence in a territory of its own (Sayegh, 2012, p. 207). The aspiration for a Jewish State came to fruition in 1917 when the British Government endorsed the Balfour Declaration, affirming the intention to establish "a national home for the Jewish people" in Palestine (Balfour, 1917).

Zionism was the political ideology underpinning the formation of the Jewish state, which emerged in the late nineteenth century in response to rising anti-Semitism in Europe, the failure of Jewish assimilation, and the broader context of imperialism and racial-nationalist thought (Kayyali, 1977). Zionism advocated for the establishment of a Jewish homeland, originally envisioned in Palestine, and sought the support of Western imperial powers to achieve this goal (Kayyali, 1977; Malik et al., 2023). Zionism aligned with Western imperial interests, particularly British imperial strategy in the Middle East. In fact, Zionist leaders, particularly Theodor Herzl, viewed the future Jewish state as not only a sanctuary for Jews but also a strategic outpost for Western imperial interests (Kayyali, 1977).

Following the Balfour Declaration, Jewish immigrants began to establish roots in Palestine, altering its demographic landscape and sparking tensions with Arab Palestinians (Hayes, 2023). As tensions over the land increased, the United Nations proposed the 1947 Partition Plan to officially divide Palestine into separate Jewish and Arab states. However, the British government and Palestinian leadership rejected the plan (Hayes, 2023). Despite this rejection, the State of Israel was declared in 1948 (Sayegh, 2012).

Zionism served not only as a liberation movement for Jews but also as a settler-colonial project that aimed to establish a Jewish state in a land already inhabited by an indigenous Arab population (Malik et al., 2023). Central to this settler-colonial project were religious and racial narratives that promoted the idea of Jewish racial unity with minimal or no Arab presence (Kayyali, 1977). Consequently, for the establishment of the Jewish State, Arab Palestinians could not continue living in their homeland. As a result, Jewish settlers started what is known as the 1948 *Nakba*, the forced dispossession and displacement of 85% of native Palestinians living on the land (Malik et al., 2023).

To this day, the people of Palestine have lived through more than 55 years of Israeli military occupation, 15 years of the Gaza blockade, internal conflicts, and constant escalations of hostilities between Israeli forces and Palestinian armed groups (OCHA, 2023). This research paper focuses on the witnessing of the most recent escalation of hostilities, which started on 7 October 2023, when the Palestinian armed group Hamas launched Operation Al-Aqsa Flood—a surprise attack that combined breaching security barriers, such as the Beit Hanoun crossing, and a bombardment of rockets fired from Gaza (Al Jazeera, 2023). Following that, the Israeli army launched Operation Iron Swords in the Gaza Strip (Al Jazeera, 2023).

From 7 October 2023 to March 2024, according to the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs, more than 1.7 million Palestinians have been internally displaced, more than 31,000 Palestinians have been killed (against 1,200 reported fatalities from Israel), and nearly 74,000 injuries have been reported. Over 60% of Gaza's housing units have been destroyed, hospitals are experiencing critical shortages of drugs, blood, fuel, and other supplies, and 1.1 million people are projected to face catastrophic levels of food insecurity (OCHA, 2024).

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter is structured by thematic groupings which outline and synthesise existing theories and research relevant to this study.

The Mediatisation of Conflict

Even though the underlying causes of conflict (such as national, ethnic, or class conflicts) remain consistent over time, the way in which conflicts are enacted has drastically changed in contemporary societies due to the widespread influence of media (Eskjaer et al., 2015). Whilst researchers have agreed for a long time with the idea that media's discursive framing of wars can deeply influence public perceptions of conflict (see, for example, Allan and Zelizer, 2004), they are now aware that this is only one of the many ways in which media can influence conflicts (Eskjaer et al., 2015). As Eskjaer et al. (2015) put

it, the contemporary relationship between media and wars can be understood as “a movement from *mediation of conflict* to *mediatisation of conflict*” (Eskjaer et al., 2015, p. 5).

This distinction between mediated or mediatised conflicts was originally developed by Simon Cottle (2006), and it refers to the idea that media not only report on conflicts, but have also become an integral part of wars themselves. Media establishments have the potential to influence the power balance between the involved parties by maintaining public legitimacy, as well as the internal organisation of conflicts and their external development (Eskjaer et al., 2015, p. 3). As the founder of the organisation WITNESS explains, “a camera at the right time at the right place can be more powerful than tanks and guns [...] we are watching so they can no longer keep their deeds hidden” (Hayes, 2023).

However, media systems are deeply embedded within existing power structures (Kaempf, 2013). During times of conflict, control over media resources becomes particularly crucial, as the distribution of these resources often reflects existing structural inequalities between the parties involved (Eskjaer et al., 2015). For instance, in the context of Israel and Palestine, studies like the one conducted by Saba (2021) have proven that violence against Palestinians is frequently underreported, with media coverage predominantly adopting Israeli narratives. This bias in reporting highlights the power imbalance that allows dominant powers to control and shape the narrative of events (Ciuriak, 2021). This has often turned the media into a powerful propaganda tool, where information is presented in a way that reinforces the status quo and marginalises dissenting voices (Perez et al., 2023).

The influence that media and information technologies have on conflicts has been exemplified by the recent Russian invasion of Ukraine. Scholars have described this war as “the first full-blown social media war” (Ciurak, 2022, p. 2) since the unparalleled communication strategy of Ukrainian President Zelensky had a profound impact on the way that the conflict developed (Serafin, 2022; Vidal Egea, 2022). During the conflict, President Zelensky participated in multiple public appearances that went viral on social media, such as his speech at the Grammy Music Awards or at the Glastonbury music festival (Serafin, 2022). Additionally, he used his own social media platforms to give daily broadcasts about the war (Serafin, 2022). This, according to scholars such as Serafin (2022) and Vidal Egea (2022), helped nurture a profound sense of empathy globally towards Ukraine, which Zelensky hoped would become a decisive factor between victory and surrender (Vidal Egea, 2022, p. 461).

The Dynamics of Mediatised Conflicts

Eskjaer et al. (2015) suggest three dynamics that digital media has introduced for mediatised conflicts that play an important role in the development of conflicts: conduits, languages, and environments (Eskjaer et al., 2015, p. 9).

1. **Conduits:** These scholars argue that the media can act as conduits by amplifying conflicts across time and space and by increasing audience reach (Eskjaer et al., 2015). Put simply, digital media enables the amplification of conflicts, on one hand, by reaching new audiences that do not consume traditional mainstream media or that live in a different geographical location, and on the other hand, by sharing messages at a speed which would be difficult to achieve through other channels (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022; Perez et al., 2023). In the Palestinian context, Palestinians are subjected to physical restrictions that prevent them from moving freely between territories, and their voices have been constantly neglected or censored by mainstream media (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022). However, digital media enables them to share their lived experiences internationally and gather support from other communities (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022).
2. **Languages:** Similar to languages, media have a signifying function (framing) and a performative function (performative agency). Historically, governments and political elites have enjoyed an information monopoly on wars due to the interrelationship between media systems and power structures (Kaempf, 2013). This information monopoly refers to the ability to act as media gatekeepers by filtering which information is presented to the public (Rusdi and Rusdi, 2020). In this sense, state authorities such as the army utilise media organisations to inform the public of their interpretation of a certain conflict in a way that benefits them (Eskjaer et al., 2015). In the case of Israel’s settler colonialism, the State of Israel cooperates with international governments and broadcasters to censor Palestinian voices and it asserts influence in how the genocide is framed (Pycinska, 2023). For instance, multiple studies (Philo and Berry, 2004; Richardson and Barkho, 2009, as cited in Hayes, 2023) showed that British mainstream media channels such as

BBC avoid using terms such as “occupation,” “Zionism” or “colonialism,” and instead they frame the situation as “cycles of violence,” “self-defence,” or “security” (Hayes, 2023, p. 39). However, the expansion of digital media has enabled new actors such as private citizens and grassroots organisations to contribute to the public discourse of conflicts (Kaempf, 2013; Eskjaer et al., 2015; Harlow, 2017; Serafin, 2022).

- Additionally, mainstream media has traditionally framed conflicts through what Said (1978) called ‘othering’—the construction of binary pairs such as good/evil, civilisation/savagery, or order/chaos. This can be exemplified by *The Guardian* article published during the temporary ceasefire in Gaza in November 2023, where the writer referred to Israeli prisoners as “women and *children*,” whereas they referred to Palestinian prisoners as “women and *people under 18*.” This small differentiation could change public perceptions and significantly influence the empathy readers might feel for the different sides. However, as previously mentioned, digital media can change dominant narratives and “systems of meaning” by challenging “mainstream ideas on justice, victimhood, and friend/enemy relationships and [by] proposing alternative versions of identity” (Chouliaraki and Kissas, 2018, p. 26).
 - Importantly, how media constructs and manipulates narratives can also serve to villainise certain groups. By selectively highlighting violence and framing it in a way that presents one side as morally superior or justified, media outlets can shape public perception, reinforcing biases and further entrenching conflict (Chouliaraki, 2015; Siddiqua and Sultan, 2021). As Siddiqua and Sultan (2021) demonstrate in their study of Western media representations of Islam and Muslims, this manipulation of narratives often exploits pre-existing stereotypes or creates new ones, intensifying hostility and supporting the agendas of those in power.
 - Moreover, performative agency is another function that media may have as languages. As Eskjaer et al. (2015) explain, “actors can perform in particular ways, resulting in a particular dramaturgy of the conflict in question” (Eskjaer et al., 2015, p. 9). This performance includes not only what is presented on the image, but also all the previous choices made before the image reaches the audience (the production of the image, the camera angle, the emotional expressions shown, and so forth) (Hayes, 2023). Depending on how this content is presented, it has the potential to appeal to emotions, which can motivate viewers to stop what they are seeing (Hayes, 2023).
3. Environments: Media as ‘environments’ refers to the fact that media practices are embedded in structural relations of power; they are involved in the *co-structuring* of power in terms of access to and control over communicative resources during conflicts (Eskjaer et al., 2015). As previously mentioned, due to the emergence of digital technologies, ordinary citizens can now participate in the co-structuring of power by posting, sharing, and promoting content that emphasises different aspects or sides of a conflict, which consequently allows them to become directly involved in the mediatisation of wars (Kaempf, 2013). This can be exemplified by the use of amateur videos, which, according to Chouliaraki (2015), reinforce feelings of credibility and truth and are frequently used as a means to represent the perspectives of traditionally disadvantaged groups during a conflict.

These dynamics of mediatised conflicts are deeply intertwined with the concept of distant or digital witnesses (Gregory, 2015; Chouliaraki, 2015), which will be explained in the next section.

Witnessing

Digital Witnessing

Agreeing on a definition of witnessing has proven to be a difficult task for many scholars. However, for this paper, I will define it as “the discursive act of stating one’s experience for the benefit of an audience that was not present at the event and yet must make some kind of judgement about it” (Peters, 2008, p. 25). As technology has become increasingly intertwined with society, the idea of bearing witness to events has transcended traditional boundaries and has evolved into what Chouliaraki (2015) terms ‘digital witnessing’. Digital witnessing refers to the power that individuals possess to document and share their lived experiences with the world through the use of technology such as smartphones or digital media platforms such as social media sites (Chouliaraki, 2015).

Consequently, journalists, correspondents, and individuals involved in a conflict are not the only witnesses; but newsreaders, television audiences, and social media users can also be witnesses of an event

even if they are not present at the time it happened (Peters, 2008; Gregory, 2015). Even though war reporters and traditional press platforms continue to play an essential role in the communication of wars, the rise of digital technologies has resulted in the transformation of one's ability to bear witness. In fact, most breaking news is often captured and shared by participants or witnesses on the ground, rather than by journalists in the mainstream media (Eskjaer et al., 2015). This has resulted in a new hybrid media system in which mainstream media companies, such as Al Jazeera, use citizen journalism alongside traditional reporting on a regular basis (Hayes, 2023).

Witnessing also bears a legal component since visual evidence has a strong association with crime and punishment (Linfield, 2010, as cited in Allan, 2017). As Harlow (2017) points out, in contrast to verbal or written testimony, visual media has become the most convincing form of evidence that can be used to report human rights abuses in courts of law (see Hayes, 2023). Additionally, witnessing has a moral or spiritual dimension which stems from Judeo-Christian practices of testifying (Felman and Laub, 1992, as cited in Peters, 2008). As Peters (2008) puts it:

“Witnessing is an intricately tangled practice. It raises questions of truth and experience, presence and absence, death, and pain, seeing and saying, and the trustworthiness of perception—in short, fundamental questions of communication.”

Digital witnessing serves multiple purposes, such as representing victims' perspectives, communicating moral values, humanising individuals in conflict zones, and providing evidence for legal cases (Chouliaraki, 2015; Gregory, 2015; Harlow, 2017). Through testimonies and content shared online, victims can share their experiences, highlight ethical concerns, and foster empathy. This practice helps humanise those affected by violence and holds perpetrators accountable (Harlow, 2017). Nevertheless, there are risks and challenges associated with the practice of digital witnessing that should be addressed.

Critical Debates

Research on digital witnessing reveals some risks and challenges that should be considered when examining the potential of digital content in the mediatisation of wars: the verification of images and their admissibility in legal cases, the privacy and safety of activists, social media algorithms, and 'slacktivism'.

Verification And Admissibility

One of the main discussions regarding digital witnessing revolves around the verification of images. Some scholars have argued that social media platforms are flooded with misinformation, as well as staged or distorted images (Perez et al., 2023). The fact that citizens are the ones recording the images raises concerns about their authenticity and reliability (Eskjaer et al., 2015). However, traditional media platforms also share highly edited images, biased articles, and provocative and manipulative comments (Eskjaer et al., 2015). Therefore, this risk is not isolated to social media platforms. In relation to the verification of images, there are doubts regarding their legitimacy and admissibility when they are presented as evidence in legal cases (Ellis, 2015). To address these concerns, the International Bar Association developed the 'eyeWitness to Atrocities' mobile app, which safely records and stores the date, time, and GPS location of the images so that they can be verified and used in court cases to bring perpetrators of human rights abuses to justice (Ellis, 2015).

Privacy and Safety

The literature also raises concerns regarding the privacy and safety of activists. Returning to the earlier point about legal proceedings, individuals may not realise they might be implicated in lengthy legal investigations as witnesses due to the content they share on social media (Harlow, 2017). In addition to the time implications those kinds of investigations require, reliving such experiences may also have deep psychological consequences (Harlow, 2017). Additionally, activists' electronic footprints can be easily tracked and identified by governments if they are not properly trained on what should or should not be documented, which can put them in dangerous situations (Gregory, 2015).

Algorithms

Another key challenge is the algorithmic filtering, censoring and other policies that online platforms have in place that can complicate their use for online activism and digital witnessing. Regardless of whether these platforms are used for human rights activism, they were not originally designed for this purpose. Instead, they are created by corporations with commercial interests that promote or censor content at their discretion (Harlow, 2017; Hayes, 2023). For instance, some scholars have found that Facebook's

moderation policies exhibit a pro-Israel leaning by promoting Israeli content while censoring or deleting Palestinian content (Aouragh, 2016; Nashif and Fatafta, 2017, as cited in Hayes, 2023). The consequences of such biases are far-reaching. Namely, they limit the ability of Palestinians and other marginalised groups to share their lived experiences, directly undermining efforts to raise global awareness of human rights abuses and fuelling imbalanced narratives (Hayes, 2023). For instance, during the 2021 escalation between Israel and Hamas, Israeli Justice Minister Benny Gantz met with executives from Facebook and TikTok to urge them to remove content that, according to him, incited violence and encouraged attacks against Israelis (Giella, 2021). He claimed that "extremist elements" were using social media platforms to spread misinformation and stir unrest, particularly among Arab citizens of Israel (Giella, 2021). This highlights some of the limitations of using digital media as a tool for activism when mechanisms of power are embedded in the platforms themselves.

Slacktivism

Lastly, scholars have raised concerns about 'slacktivism' and how online activism translates into "real" activism (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022). In simple terms, some argue that online activism is a "lazy" practice where individuals substitute offline participation with simply boosting their online presence or keeping up appearances without translating into any real-life involvement (Harlow, 2017; Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022). However, slacktivism can also be a symptom of compassion fatigue—being exposed to an overload of distressing images of human suffering which often results in detachment, desensitisation, and the loss of the emotional capacity to respond in a meaningful way (Sontag, 2003; Hayes, 2023). In this sense, instead of turning away entirely, some people might engage in symbolic acts of support (by liking or sharing a post), which allow them to show concern and support without the emotional burden of deeper involvement. However, many studies have shown that small acts of engagement (such as liking a post, sharing images, and joining a group) improve the visibility of an issue and can promote offline engagement (see, for example, Bode, 2017). Additionally, as Papacharissi (2015) argues, to understand contemporary forms of activism, it is imperative that researchers implement a broader analytical scope, encompassing not just traditional forms of political participation but also embracing informal and individualised channels of political expression.

Framing The Palestinian Struggle on Tiktok

Israel has developed a unique and multi-layered system of surveillance that includes physical technologies (such as CCTV systems, x-ray machines, drones in occupied territories, and digital technologies) that monitor communications (such as phone calls, messages, and social media posts) in both Palestine and the wider diaspora (Hayes 2023; Pycinska 2023). Consequently, this "digital occupation" (Tawil-Souri, 2012) has resulted in a mixed experience for Palestinians online. Settler-colonialism enforces a disconnection between the occupied communities and their land by erasing their history and culture (Zidani, 2021). However, as Zidani (2021) argues, the use of digital media allows diasporic communities to recast ideas of land and to articulate their personal subjectivities through oral history.

Particularly on TikTok, Palestinians have been able to create communities of supporters and celebrate their culture by becoming "storytellers" of their experiences under occupation (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2023, p. 428). Additionally, Palestinians use TikTok as "everyday forms of resistance" by recording themselves continuing with their normal lives in occupied territories instead of fleeing (Scott, 1989 p. 34, as cited in Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022). Palestinians have also used TikTok regularly to recruit more activists during attacks and to educate people about their struggles (Perez et al., 2023). For instance, TikTok became flooded with videos in support of Palestine after the Sheikh Jarrar evictions in 2021 (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022). Palestinian activism on TikTok has become so widespread that scholars speak of a "TikTok Intifada" (Abbas et al., 2022) to represent the Palestinian resistance against Internet restrictions imposed by Israel. However, it is important to recognise that TikTok, like other social media platforms, is not a neutral space but a commercially driven platform shaped by corporate and political interests (Harlow, 2017; Perez et al., 2023). This raises critical questions about whose interests the platform ultimately serves, especially given the role of algorithmic moderation and potential censorship of pro-Palestinian content as discussed in section 2.2.2—practices which may undermine the very forms of resistance it enables.

METHODOLOGY

Positionality

As I embark on the journey of researching the witnessing of the Israeli occupation of Gaza through TikTok, it is essential to acknowledge the complexities of my positionality as a researcher. My identity,

background, and experiences undoubtedly shape my perspective and influence the way I approach this research topic.

Firstly, I am a white woman conducting research within a Western university setting, without any personal ties to Palestine. This aspect of my identity highlights my outsider status within the context of the Israeli occupation of Gaza (Darwin Holmes, 2020). My lack of direct experience or intimate knowledge of Palestinian culture, history, and lived realities may impact my understanding and interpretation of the events witnessed through TikTok.

Furthermore, my positionality gives me certain privileges and biases. These privileges may include access to resources, academic networks, and institutional support, which can influence my research process and outcomes. Therefore, it was important for me to reflect on the language I use in this article. There are norms in Western universities that dictate what is deemed appropriate language and what is considered radical (Snounu, 2021). Even though terms such as “conflict” or “self-defence” appear to be neutral, they have constantly been used to justify Israeli violence against Palestinians. For that reason, this paper will use terminology such as “apartheid” or “occupation,” that is widely accepted and used by activists, advocacy organisations, and international human rights organisations (Hayes, 2023).

Despite my positionality as an outsider to the Palestinian community, I approach my research with humility, sensitivity, and a commitment to amplifying the voices of those directly affected by the Israeli occupation. While I cannot fully comprehend the lived experiences of Palestinians in Gaza, I strive to engage in ethical and reflexive research practices that centre their narratives and prioritise their agency.

Lastly, research has been and continues to be used as a tool for reinforcing colonial ideas and structures (Smith, 2012). For that reason, it is crucial to consider my positionality as a student from a colonial country. In conducting this research, I recognise the ethical responsibilities inherent in representing the experiences of others, particularly in a context marked by ongoing conflict and oppression. I am mindful of the power dynamics at play and the potential impact of my research on the communities involved. Therefore, I commit to centring ethical considerations, maintaining transparency, and interrogating my own biases throughout the research process.

Methods

Results from a review of social media studies found that qualitative approaches are more often used with methods such as interviews or surveys to understand experiences and behaviour of using social media (Snelson, 2016, as cited in Hayes, 2023). However, more recently, there has been an increasing awareness of the importance of language and meaning, which combined with an expansion of the power of mass media and social media platforms, has resulted in a dramatic increase in the interest in textual analysis (Halperin and Heath, 2020). For that reason, this study will be conducted using discourse analysis.

As Halperin and Heath (2020) explain, discourse analysis is concerned with analysing the text itself, along with its context (source, message, channel, intended audience, connection to other texts and events) and “the broader relations of power and authority within that context” (Halperin and Heath, 2020, p. 479). In other words, discourse analysis aims not only to uncover meanings by examining the language people use in their interactions, but also to reveal how language practices shape meanings through creating, spreading, and consuming various forms of texts. (Halperin and Heath, 2020, p. 481).

Data Collection

Choice Of Social Media Platforms

Much of the previous research studies about social media platforms as political tools have largely focused on Facebook, X, YouTube, and, more recently, Instagram. However, the success of TikTok since its global launch in 2018 has become indisputable, and it now enjoys over 1.12 billion monthly active users (Dean, 2023). On average, TikTok users spend 55 minutes a day on the app, and more than 34 million videos are posted each day (Daniel, 2023). According to a report published by Rival IQ in 2023, TikTok’s average engagement rate per follower is 5.7%, which is significantly higher compared to Instagram’s 1.72% or Facebook’s 0.82% (Feehan, 2023). Additionally, TikTok has become one of the platforms with the greatest capacity for message amplification, thanks to its algorithm’s performance (Cervi et al., 2022; Perez Rastrilla et al., 2023). Consequently, its effects on the political arena have surpassed all expectations, which has made communication professionals and academics closely follow its use and consolidation as a channel

for political communication (Perez Rastrilla et al., 2023). For these reasons, this research will focus on analysing videos from TikTok recorded during the Israeli occupation of Gaza.

Inclusion Criteria for Posts

To be included in the sample, videos had to meet the following criteria: 1) recorded by civilians in Gaza, 2) specifically created for TikTok, and 3) downloadable. Videos were downloaded by using the 'share' function available on the TikTok app; if the creator allowed their videos to be downloaded, an option to save the video was included in the share function. Videos were not included if they were re-posted from other media (clips from television news, for instance), or if they were from private accounts or not downloadable. Videos in English, Arabic, and Hebrew were all included; only images were analysed if captions were not available.

The Process of Data Collection

I collected data between October 2023 and January 2024. Since TikTok does not have a public Application Programming Interface (API), I decided to collect data manually. While using an API can provide a large amount of data, it also requires deciding in advance which specific data to collect by establishing a set of rules (Hayes, 2023). In contrast, manual data collection allowed for greater flexibility and ensured that only relevant data was gathered, which is also considered more ethical (ICO, 2021, as cited in Hayes, 2023).

To ensure that there was an archive of the data and to protect the data in case posts were removed during the analysis process, I downloaded all videos and recorded their links in a spreadsheet. Once in the spreadsheet, I analysed the videos based on the variables shown in Table 1. I developed these variables by combining categories from previous literature with those I identified inductively after watching an initial subset of the videos.

For instance, the 'availability' variable was included after reading Harlow's (2017) research on live witnessing, where she pointed out that censoring in some countries can result in content being shadowbanned or completely deleted. The variable 'language' was included because, according to Hjarvard, Mortensen, and Eskjaer (2015), language plays a part in the framing and amplification of conflicts; additionally, after watching some videos, I noticed that many of them were in English even though Arabic is the main language in Palestine. For the 'style' variable, I took inspiration from Perez et al.'s (2023) paper 'Fast Politics', where the authors study bodily communication. There, they point out the centrality of the body in TikTok videos, and they argue that the body is used as a channel of expression that inspires trust and emotions (Perez et al., 2023, pp. 25-26).

I identified all of the categories in the 'dominant narrative' variable inductively by watching the videos and organising them into five different categories that best summarised their content. Although some videos contained multiple narratives, I assigned each video to only one category for analysis purposes. To do this, I considered all elements of the video—sound, images, text, and so forth—to categorise them as accurately as possible. Each category had specific fixed elements that needed to appear in the video for it to be classified under that group. For example, if a video primarily featured someone discussing their experiences living in refugee camps—such as where they sleep, what they eat, or how they bathe—I categorised it under 'living conditions.'

The variable 'sound' was inspired by Cervi, L. and Marin-Llado, C.'s (2022) study on playful activism, where they analysed TikTok videos with the hashtag #freepalestine, and they realised that many videos used the Mohammad Assaf song 'Dammi Falastini' (My Blood is Palestinian), which has become an unofficial anthem for the Palestinian cause (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022, p. 419). Therefore, I also recorded the names of songs used in the videos I analysed. Cervi's and Marin-Llado's research also inspired the variable 'emojis', since they argue that emojis serve as a shared language that overcomes linguistic and cultural barriers and, therefore, fosters communication (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022, p. 426).

Lastly, for the 'direct calls to action' variable, I drew on a study by Abbas et al. (2022), in which they analysed over 200 TikTok videos supporting Palestine during the Sheikh Jarrah evictions in 2021. Their findings revealed that nearly 60% of the videos included calls to action (Abbas et al., 2022, p. 299), which informed my approach to analysing this variable in my research.

Variables	Code	Description
Availability	Yes/no	Is the TikTok post still available online or has it been taken down by the platform/user?
Language	English	Is the subject being recorded talking to the camera in English? (This did not include subtitles in English)
	Arab	Is the subject being recorded talking to the camera in Arabic?
	No voice	No presence of voice
Dominant narrative	Living conditions	Living conditions in refugee camps, conditions of hospitals and healthcare, and descriptions of personal hygiene.
	Displacement	Images of displacement, evacuation bags, warnings for evacuation of areas, and references to the 1948 Nakba.
	Death/mourning	Images of martyrs, people mourning relatives, people looking in the rubble for lost relatives.
	Bombings/destruction	Images of bombings, images of cities/buildings after bombings.
	Happy or hopeful moments	Re-encounters with family, images of children playing/singing/painting, images of people finding food and other items after weeks without.
Style	Vlog yes/no	Do the subjects interact with the camera as if they were recording a vlog rather than simply posting footage without context?
Sound	Song/original sound	Is the video accompanied by a song or is there live audio?
Direct calls to action	Yes/no	Does the video include direct calls to action for people watching?
Emojis	Yes/no	Does the video include emojis?

Table 1. Summary of how the data is categorised in the analysis.

I also included a short description of each video in the spreadsheet, which helped to identify more specific details such as TikTok trends (for example, “a day in the life of [...]”). Additionally, I manually collected important metadata from the videos, including the number of likes, comments, and shares, and recorded it in the spreadsheet.

Validity

The validity of a discourse-analytic study can be determined in terms of two different factors: its credibility and its ‘fruitfulness’ (Halperin and Heath, 2020). To put it simply, it should provide an interpretation of the text that is clearly related to the textual evidence, an analysis which is ‘credible, plausible [and] coherent’ (Halperin and Heath, 2020, p. 491), as well as aiming to provide insights that prove to be useful.

This study analyses a small sample of videos (N=230), and therefore it might not be generalisable to other wars or occupations. However, this is not the goal of this research. This research is fruitful in the way in which it shows how TikTok has been used by Palestinian people, and how that has challenged the monopoly of information held by mainstream media.

Ethical Considerations

One big ethical consideration I encountered when carrying out this research was whether social media data should be considered private or public. I ended up considering the data public since only data that was posted by public accounts and had the option to be downloaded was analysed. I made this decision following the British Psychological Association (2021) guidelines, which state that “where it is reasonable to argue that there is likely no perception and/or expectation of privacy [...] use of research data without gaining valid consent may be justifiable” (Oates, 2021, p. 9). The current general opinion within social media research is that data that has been posted publicly has implicit consent (Jordan, 2018). However, many videos were taken down from TikTok after they were downloaded, and there is no way to know if it was done by the platform or the user. Therefore, when including examples, this article will only use videos that are still publicly available to ensure it does not violate users’ right to oblivion.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

TikTok as ‘Conduits’: Amplification

TikTok has been described by some scholars as the platform with the biggest capacity for message amplification (Perez et al., 2023). Considering the physical and digital restrictions that Palestinian people are subjected to, TikTok appears as a key resource used to amplify struggles and reach new audiences. Palestinian users have used a multitude of techniques to achieve maximum reach for their videos.

Language

Firstly, even though Palestinian Arabic is the most spoken language in Palestine (The Palestinian Centre), 64.1% of the videos analysed in the sample were in English, and most videos in Arabic had subtitles in English. This shows that the target audiences were nations outside of Palestine, which is an attempt to increase the visibility of the events globally.

More interestingly, TikTok users have a ‘shared vernacular’ they use to communicate (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022, p. 426). This can be exemplified by Images 2 and 3, which show the use of special characters to distort words to avoid videos being taken down by the platform. For instance, ‘m4rtyred’ instead of ‘martyred’; ‘hosp1tal’ instead of ‘hospital’; or ‘b0mbed’ instead of ‘bombed’. These adaptations not only reflect a collective digital resistance to platform control, but also highlight how activism is shaped by the technical affordances and constraints of each social media platform. As a result, the very design of TikTok makes users engage in creative forms of resistance, reinforcing the idea that the platform is both a tool for visibility and a site of contested control.

Image 2. Free Palestine [@free.palestine1160] This is what some of the child in Gaza has been experiencing #freepalestine #gaza crdts IG:a7mhisham. TikTok. 01/11/23. Last accessed 12/03/24.

Image 3. Eye on Palestine [@eyes_on_palestine] #Palestine #Gaza #Gazaunderattack #freepalestine #humanity. TikTok. 29/10/23. Last accessed 12/03/24.

Length Of Videos

Initially, TikTok videos were limited to 30-second clips (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022). In 2022, the platform expanded the maximum length to 10 minutes (TikTok, 2024). However, according to the ‘goldfish effect’, which highlights the increasing decline in the attention span of humans, from 12 seconds to 8.25 seconds in the last couple of decades (Golden Steps, 2023), users still prefer shorter videos (Perez et al., 2023). The average video length in this study is 60 seconds, while videos classified as viral (>250,000 views) average 58 seconds. Notably, the two most viral videos, each with 1.4 million views, are just 11 and 15 seconds long, which is consistent with the goldfish effect.

Use Of TikTok Trends

Based on previous studies about the use of TikTok during wartime (for instance, Vidal, 2022; Ciurak, 2022; Serafin, 2022 on the use of TikTok by Ukrainians during the war with Russia) and on the existing literature regarding Palestinian activism on TikTok (for instance Abbas et al., 2022 or Hayes, 2023), I expected a widespread use of TikTok trends by Palestinians to boost their content and reach new audiences during the occupation. However, only 5.7% of the videos in the sample contained TikTok trends such as the one in Image 4. This suggests that Palestinian users may be prioritising authenticity, personal storytelling, or direct documentation of lived experiences over algorithmic optimisation. Rather than performing for virality, many appear to be engaging in a form of witnessing and resistance that is grounded in political urgency rather than digital popularity.

Image 4. Salma [@anat_international] Put together these clips Nisreen took to show you all a “day in the life” in Gaza. While influencers do their relaxing comfortable day in the life vlogs, remember that this is the life other are living during these moments [...] #dayinthelife #vlog. TikTok. 12/12/23. Last accessed 12/03/24.

TikTok As ‘Languages’: Framing and Performative Agency

As presented in Chapter 3, media can act as ‘languages’ by framing conflicts following a particular narrative, and by performing the conflicts for the camera in a particular way (Eskjaer et al., 2015). According to previous studies (Hayes, 2023; Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022; Perez et al., 2023), this includes the production of the image as much as the content of the image. Consequently, this research analysed four different components of each TikTok video: the use of music, the style of the videos, the dominant narrative in each video, and the use of emojis.

Use Of Music

One of TikTok’s affordances is how user-friendly the creation process is by allowing users to integrate professional tools in a very intuitive way (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022). One of the most used tools to enhance TikTok videos’ narratives is music; each song has its own sound page, which makes it extremely easy to find videos or replicate trends associated with a song (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022). In this

research analysis, 28.9% of the 230 videos examined were accompanied by a song. The rest of the videos used original sound, which means that the audio featured in the TikTok wasn't added during the editing phase; instead, it originated from the video itself, such as the creator speaking directly into the microphone (Badola, 2023).

One of the songs that was repeatedly used was 'Dammi Falastini' (My Blood is Palestinian), a song created by Mohammad Assaf, a Palestinian musician that grew up in the Khan Younis refugee camp in Gaza (Al Jazeera, 2023). This song originally went viral during the Sheikh Jarrah evictions in 2021 (Al Jazeera, 2023). Since then, it has become an anthem to express Palestinian culture and its political grievances (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022). This song alone accumulates more than 1.2M posts on its sound page (TikTok, 2024).

Similarly, the song 'We Will Not Go Down' by Michael Heart regained popularity on TikTok during the ongoing invasion, with more than 163,600 posts (TikTok, 2024). The song was originally released in 2009 as a symbol of support for Palestine after the Gaza Massacre in December 2008 (VOI, 2021). Another important song for the representation of Palestinians on TikTok during the invasion is 'Where Is the Love'. This original Black Eyed Peas song was rewritten by Lauren Amour in 2022 in support of Ukraine (Robinson, 2023), and it has now been reused by many creators in support of Palestine.

As previously discussed in Chapter 3, Palestinians become "storytellers" on social media as a form of resistance, and this emotionally and politically charged music helps them do so by creatively contributing to their storylines (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022).

Style

Another distinguishing feature of TikTok, as highlighted by Perez et al. (2023), is its emphasis on bodily communication, setting it apart from other social media platforms that use other types of media, which emphasise text as a means of communication. Moreover, TikTok distinguishes itself from traditional communication channels, such as TV, through its interactivity and emphasis on self-representation through the body (Perez et al., 2023). Since the body here is considered a key mechanism of discourse, this research looked at whether the videos had a vlog-like style. To determine this, the research considered the angle of the camera, the distance between the subject and the camera, whether the subject was looking directly at the camera, and the emotional expressions the subject showed. These, according to the existing literature, are important factors in determining the sympathy and closeness a witness feels towards the subject of a video (Hayes, 2023). Forty-six percent of the videos included in the study were recorded in a vlog-like style, such as the ones shown in Images 5 and 6.

Image 5. Wizard_bisani [@wizard_bisani] TikTok. 17/11/23. Last accessed 12/03/24.

Image 6. Gaza Press [@gazapressheroes] TikTok. 18/11/23. Last accessed 12/03/24.

Images 5 and 6 show Bisan Owda and Motaz Azaiza, respectively, who have gained millions of followers on TikTok since the beginning of the invasion due to their daily updates and livestreams from the Gaza Strip. They represent just a fraction of the civilians who have been using TikTok to document the ongoing tragedy. Research suggests that when individuals can connect a face to the suffering, they are more inclined to take action or offer assistance, a phenomenon known as the identifiable victim effect (Hayes, 2023). Bisan has gained recognition through a distinctive practice of opening her videos with the statement, “Hello, this is Bisan from Gaza, and I’m still alive.” This can be considered a form of resistance in two ways: primarily through the act of “merely” surviving and still existing, and secondly, by demonstrating her willingness to continue reporting on the atrocities unfolding in Gaza, despite facing numerous obstacles and fears.

Less staged vlog-style videos are perceived as more personal, evoking emotional responses from viewers and motivating them to take action (Perez et al., 2023). According to Golick (2023), a TikTok video must have a minimum of 250,000 likes to qualify as viral. Based on this criterion, only 20% of the videos examined in the study meet the viral threshold, and vlogs represent 54% of those videos considered viral. This suggests that individuals such as Bisan and Motaz have successfully established an emotional bond with their audiences, earning their trust and emerging as symbols of the Palestinian struggle (Image 7). In fact, after Motaz Azaiza managed to evacuate from Gaza, he received awards such as the TRT’s World Citizen Communicator Award “for transparently reflecting the realities of Palestinians through real-time updates from Gaza” (TRT, 2023). Additionally, Bisan Owda received an Emmy Award in the Hard News Feature Story category for her reporting on the atrocities in the Gaza Strip (Al Jazeera, 2024).

Image 7. Picture taken by @zahrasalmanasif during a protest in London, 2023. X.

Lastly, the fact that teenagers and young adults are the ones starring in these vlogs could also influence their popularity. According to Durham (2018), not all victims have the same impact on viewers, and images of children usually have the biggest emotional reactions. Most of the individuals that have gone viral and accumulated a big following on TikTok are under 30 years old—Bisan Owda (25), Plestia Alaqaad (22), Hind Khoudary (29), Motaz Azaiza (25), to name a few (The New Arab, 2024).

Most Prominent Message Frames

Media can shape what conflict means to different people by giving a particular interpretative meaning to it or by enhancing a particular narrative (Eskjaer et al., 2015). The different narrative frames used during the reporting of a conflict help construct archives and a collective memory of the event (Eskjaer et al., 2015). This could prove especially valuable for communities like the Palestinian people, who seek to offer alternative narratives to those put forth by mainstream Western media, which frequently exhibit bias towards Israeli perspectives.

During the analysis of the videos, five different narratives were identified inductively (Figure 1). The two most prominent narratives were 'living conditions' and 'bombings/destruction', which directly challenge Israeli narratives of self-defence and instead frame it as genocide and occupation. These videos show starvation, unhygienic living conditions in refugee camps, illnesses, lack of resources, destruction of cities, and bombings directed towards civilian buildings, hospitals, and refugee camps. These two narratives accounted for 54.16% of the videos that met the viral threshold in the sample: 33.33% and 20.83% respectively (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Dominant narratives identified during the data analysis process (N=230).

Figure 2. Dominant narratives from the videos that met the virality threshold (N=48).

The third most used narrative was 'death/mourning'. As Hayes (2023) argues, audiences do not respond the same to all human suffering since certain lives are deemed more deserving of grief than others. In this sense, Palestinian lives have largely been considered as collateral damage and not worthy of grief (Butler, 2009). Through depicting the pain and grieving of Palestinian individuals, these videos challenge the notion that their lives are just expendable casualties and not worth grieving. This narrative represented 27.08% of the videos that met the viral threshold in the sample.

The fourth narrative identified was 'happy/hopeful moments', which could alleviate some of the compassion fatigue that seeing an overwhelming number of images of pain and destruction could cause to audiences. This compassion fatigue, according to Hayes (2023), could lead to apathy since viewers might feel like they cannot help, leading to desensitisation among audiences towards the images. The videos in this category accounted for 10.41% of the viral videos in the sample.

Lastly, the narrative 'displacement' connects directly with the moral dimensions of witnessing. As Peters (2008) explains, one of the goals of witnessing is remembrance—being able to remember what has happened with the view of not happening again. In this sense, videos included in this narrative constantly referenced the 1948 Nakba and showed individuals who had already been through it (Image 9). This frames the events as history repeating itself. Lastly, the videos included in this narrative represented 8.33% of the viral videos in the sample.

Arguably, the most emotional narrative frames (living conditions, bombings, and death) were included in over 80% of the viral videos. This is consistent with previous studies that argue that the most powerful images are those that are able to evoke an emotional response in the viewer (Hayes, 2023).

Image 8. From left to right: Gaza Press [@gazapressheroes] TikTok. 26/12/23, example of video from 'living conditions' narrative; Mrs.potatohead [@ms.batatai] TikTok. 10/11/23 example of 'displacement'; Ibrahim Muammar [@ibrahimmuammar7] TikTok. 13/12/23 example of 'death/mourning'; Mj [@mj_1118] TikTok. 05/11/23 example of 'bombings/destruction'; Ella [@becauseitsright] TikTok. 27/12/23 example of 'happy/hopeful moments'. Last accessed 12/03/24.

Use Of Emojis

As mentioned in section 4.1.1, TikTok users communicate using a shared vernacular (Cervi and Marin-Llado, 2022), and emojis are part of this shared language. Emojis, as explained by Hayes (2023), serve as non-verbal communication tools that enable people to convey emotions by depicting facial expressions and other common objects. Therefore, they can be used to frame a particular narrative since they show users' emotions. However, they can also be used to amplify events since they allow users to overcome linguistic barriers, which facilitates communication (Hayes, 2023). Nearly 20% of the videos in the sample contained emojis.

Image 9. Gaza Press [@gazapressheroes] TikTok. 24/12/23. Last accessed 12/03/24.

Image 10. [@resistance_waz] TikTok. 31/12/23. Last accessed 12/03/24.

Additionally, some emojis are also used to avoid surveillance and to bypass content moderation, such as the use of the watermelon emoji instead of the Palestinian flag (Mendonça et al., 2023). This is used in the same way as the distortion of words with special characters mentioned in section 4.1.1.

TikTok as 'Environments': Co-Structuring

Individuals posting TikTok videos during the occupation are participating in the co-structuring of events by positioning themselves in relation to the people carrying out the attacks. As discussed in Chapter 3, co-structuring refers to the power dynamics over the access to and control of communication resources (Eskjaer et al., 2015). When Palestinians have tried to participate in said co-structuring, they have encountered many challenges, such as threats from the Israeli army (Image 11), and total blackouts or attacks directed at cell phone towers (Image 12). This is consistent with Harlow's (2017) and Gregory's (2015) concerns regarding the safety of activists participating in digital witnessing.

Image 11. Sooooo [@sooooo52] TikTok. 07/11/23, Motaz receiving a non-caller ID phone call about his videos. Last accessed 12/03/24.

Image 12. Motaz [@_motaz_azaiza] TikTok. 18/11/23. Motaz trying to find signal to continue posting content. Last accessed 12/03/24.

Percentage of Videos Taken Down

From the original sample of 230 videos for this study, 108 videos have been removed from TikTok, which represents 46.96% of the sample. When users confronted the platform about their content being deleted, TikTok has claimed that “[it] does not moderate or remove content based on political sensitivities [...] only content that violates community guidelines, which apply equally to all content on TikTok” (TikTok spokesperson in an interview with Al Jazeera, 2023). The TikTok Community Guidelines Enforcement Report for October-December 2023 is still not available to the public. However, according to a TikTok article, more than 925,000 videos from the Middle East were deleted in the first month of the attacks “for violating [their] policies around violence, hate speech, misinformation, and terrorism” (TikTok, 2023).

While the Arab Centre for the Advancement of Social Media (2023) noted that TikTok exhibited relatively fewer violations compared to other platforms, it also highlighted TikTok's ongoing collaboration with organisations to safeguard Palestinian content. This contrast highlights the inherent tension within TikTok's role as both a platform for resistance and a company bound by political and economic interests.

Direct Calls to Action

Visual content, such as TikTok videos, can not only raise awareness about an issue and generate empathy but also encourage action (Harlow, 2017). 19.7% of the videos in the sample contained direct calls to

action—in other words, the video included calls to other nations to send aid, to join protests, to stop Israel and end the genocide. For instance, Hind Khoudary said in one of her videos: “This is not a humanitarian pause, this is not a ceasefire, and we are calling for a ceasefire right now” (Gaza Press, 2023a); similarly, Bisan says “tell the Israeli army to tell the world the truth, that they are pushing us to go outside Gaza Strip because they want to take over Gaza [...] tell the world, Israel, that you don’t want us [...] that this is a Nakba like 1948 [...] tell the world” (Gaza Press, 2023b). However, the percentage of videos that include direct calls to action is significantly lower than other studies conducted before the attacks started; for instance, the study conducted by Abbas et al. (2022) about social media activism among Palestinian youth found that 59.1% of the videos they analysed (n= 203) contained calls to action (Abbas et al., 2022, p. 299). This decrease might suggest a potential shift in the nature of Palestinian activism on TikTok. While earlier studies highlighted the platform as a key tool for direct mobilisation, the current findings suggest that Palestinians may be less inclined to use TikTok for explicit calls to action. This could reflect a growing sense of caution due to heightened digital surveillance, censorship, and potential repercussions from both the platform and the broader political environment.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this analysis was to shed light on the multifaceted role of TikTok as a digital witnessing tool during wartime. The results of the analysis show that the platform is used by Palestinian civilians to amplify their voices and reach new audiences through the creative use of language, including a shared vernacular and innovative techniques to circumvent censorship.

The findings also show that narrative framing on TikTok challenges mainstream media narratives, offering alternative perspectives on living conditions, bombings, displacement, and mourning. These narratives not only provide a counterbalance to dominant discourses on mainstream media but also foster remembrance and resistance against ongoing injustices. However, Palestinian activists face many challenges in co-structuring events on TikTok, including censorship, threats, and infrastructure disruptions. Despite these obstacles, the platform remains a vital space for direct calls to action, albeit at a lower rate compared to pre-attack periods, which indicates evolving strategies amidst changing circumstances.

The existing literature covers important topics such as the mediatisation of other wars like the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine, the strategies used for Palestinian digital activism, and the Israeli digital occupation of Palestinian voices. However, there is currently very little literature on the use of TikTok by Palestinians during wartime. For this reason, the goal of this research was to analyse the use of TikTok as a digital witnessing tool by civilians in Gaza during the ongoing attacks. To that end, it analysed 230 TikTok videos between October and December 2023 and found that short, highly emotional, vlog-style videos achieved the highest virality rate among the videos in the sample.

Whilst some TikTok affordances, such as music or trends, were sporadically used, most videos kept their original audio and did not include any trends. This represents a more amateur and less edited video format, which can be perceived as more personal and emotional. This is also consistent with the dominant narrative frames present in the 48 videos that met the viral threshold from the sample; arguably, the most emotional narrative frames—living conditions, bombings, and death—appeared in over 80% of the viral videos.

This analysis has further shown the challenges that Palestinian users may encounter when they participate in digital witnessing, such as blackouts, censorship, or threats. Additionally, it has presented some of the strategies that they have developed to avoid algorithmic filtering, censorship, and surveillance. However, since the global community has not condemned or sentenced the actions of the Israeli government thus far, this research could not include the use of images recorded for TikTok as evidence for legal proceedings and their efficacy or veracity. Therefore, it would be interesting to analyse this in future research. Furthermore, slacktivism was not addressed since the goal of the study was not to analyse if social media activities translate into traditional forms of participation; instead, it focused on how civilians are using new types of political participation. Future work could extend the present research by including analyses of the translation of digital activism into traditional or more immediate forms of civic participation.

While this research addressed censorship, it did not include any analysis of the quality of the information included in the videos. All of the videos were analysed at face value, but it is important to consider that

instances of misinformation or disinformation likely exist. Future research should consider including an analysis of the veracity of what is being shown or said in the videos.

Considering the particularities of how the Palestinian community has articulated their struggles online as a diasporic community, and how they have used TikTok as a site of resistance, as well as the large array of surveillance strategies that the Israeli government has in place to control the narrative of the events, it's important to note that this study's findings may not apply to other communities or conflicts. Although some literature exists on the use of TikTok for other wars, such as the Russia-Ukraine war, it is recommended that future research undertake a comparative analysis of various TikTok affordances and communication tactics across diverse contexts.

Because of limitations in both time and resources, this study examined a relatively small subset of videos. Additionally, nearly half of the videos within this sample were removed and therefore could not be included in the analysis. As a result, the scope of the research findings is considerably restricted, and caution should be exercised when interpreting the results. Nevertheless, this study has underscored the necessity for further investigation into the transformative capacity of TikTok as a tool for digital witnessing. This research has demonstrated TikTok's capacity as a platform for both documenting and magnifying the realities of conflicts, opening avenues for further investigation in this area.

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